

A broadening temperature sensitivity range with a core–shell YbEr@YbNd double ratiometric optical nanothermometer

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Abstract

The chemical architecture of lanthanide doped core–shell up-converting nanoparticles can be engineered to purposely design the properties of luminescent nanomaterials, which are typically inaccessible to their homogeneous counterparts. Such an approach allowed to shift the up-conversion excitation wavelength from ~980 to the more relevant ~808 nm or enable Tb or Eu up-conversion emission, which was previously impossible to obtain or inefficient. Here, we address the issue of limited temperature sensitivity range of optical lanthanide based nano-thermometers. By covering Yb–Er co-doped core nanoparticles with the Yb–Nd co-doped shell, we have intentionally combined temperature dependent Er up-conversion together with temperature dependent Nd → Yb energy transfer, and thus have expanded the temperature response range ΔT of a single nanoparticle based optical nano-thermometer under single ~808 nm wavelength photo-excitation from around $\Delta T = 150$ K to over $\Delta T = 300$ K (150–450 K). Such engineered nanocrystals are suitable for remote optical temperature measurements in technology and biotechnology at the sub-micron scale.

Introduction

Remote all-optical temperature sensing has found numerous applications in technology^{1–8} and especially in the biomedical field.^{9–11} Many different approaches have been proposed as readout parameters, such as the ratio between emission bands, luminescence absolute intensity and luminescence lifetimes.¹² Many different materials and nanomaterials have been also proposed such as quantum dots (QDs),^{12,13} dye-sensitized polymeric nanoparticles¹⁴ as well as lanthanide doped nanocrystals.^{15–17} The latter have many advantages, which include efficient anti-Stokes NIR-to-Vis conversion efficiency, high photostability, and reasonable sensitivity. The most well studied are Yb–Er co-doped up-conversion (UC) systems

where the change of the relative emission intensities of ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ to ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transitions are used for luminescent thermometry.^{15–17} By playing with dopants and host, alternative optical readout schemes have been proposed, which allowed for enhancing sensitivity, with the major focus on the physiological temperature range.⁴ Recently, significant interest has been dedicated to Nd-doped phosphors,^{18,19} which, as compared to up-converting materials, offer higher luminescence efficiency, Stokes emission in the NIR spectral region, and suitability for use as biologically relevant optical heaters,²⁰ non-contact thermometers,^{21,22} or both.^{20,22,23}

The abovementioned demands and features of optimal nano-thermometers, stimulate new discoveries and designs. For example, new NIR-to-NIR phosphors that exploit temperature dependent $\text{Nd}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Yb}^{3+}$ interionic energy transfer have been proposed as sensitive nanothermometers.²⁴ Such near-infrared-absorbing–near-infrared-emissive (NANE) materials hold great promise for biomedical applications owing to their increased readout through-the-tissue penetration depth and reduced light scattering as well as reduced absorption by water molecules (as compared to the 980 nm used in conventional UCNPs). These features make the lanthanide nano-thermometers suitable for biomedical applications—especially for monitoring the treatment progress of hyperthermia anticancer theranostics,^{24–27} where direct on-line temperature dosimetry is extremely important to control the efficient killing of cancerous cells, while protecting healthy tissues from being overheated. Interestingly, the possibility of combining heating and temperature monitoring in the same nanoparticle has been previously postulated by us and others in Nd^{3+} doped NPs.^{23,28}

Remote thermo-vision at the nano- or micro-scale is important for numerous other biological²⁹ and industrial applications^{30–32} where immediate temperature readout or temperature mapping could help studying biological processes *in vivo* or preventing damage to either mechanical or electronic components. Moreover, the remote readout, *i.e.* lack of necessity to connect the sensor with the detector, allows for remote temperature determination of rotating or moving parts of machines such as engines, turbines, rotor wings or vanes. Finally, while the readout relies on photo-excited luminescence, electrical/magnetic interaction of temperature sensors with voltage sensitive components (*e.g.* microprocessors) is prevented. The luminescent thermometers for the enumerated applications should be characterized by high absolute emission intensity, high temperature sensitivity and sufficient temperature resolution, as well as be cheap, and enable simple spot readout or temperature mapping. Lanthanide (Ln^{3+}) doped colloidal nanophosphors fulfill most of these

requirements, which make them promising candidates for remote luminescence thermometry.

Despite significant progress in optical nanothermometry many applications define additional demands and requirements, such as enhanced temperature sensitivity, colloidal stability and bio-functionalization capability of the nano-particles (NPs) used as temperature probes, as well as an enhanced temperature reading range. Up to now, the selection of hosts and dopants relied on the inherent properties of such materials, and material optimization to adjust the temperature response characteristics for a particular application was sometimes hard to achieve. This motivated us to demonstrate the possibility of purposeful design of enhanced nanothermometers by a wise combination of the components, whose behaviour and characteristics are well known. This has become possible by employing the active-core–active-shell (ACAS) approach, where core and shell host matrices are co-doped with different active rare-earth ions.

In this paper we show the design, synthesis, and characterization of such an ACAS nano-thermometer and demonstrate the enhancement of its temperature sensitivity range. The nanomaterials consist of an Yb–Er co-doped β -NaYF₄ core and an Yb–Nd co-doped β -NaYF₄ shell (termed as YbEr@YbNd) with a variable amount of Nd³⁺ in the shell. Their use was demonstrated as proof of concept of optical ratiometric NANE and UC nano-thermometers with a boosted temperature sensitivity range.

Results and discussion

The active-core/active-shell (ACAS) β -NaYF₄:Yb³⁺,Er³⁺/ β -NaYF₄: Yb³⁺,Nd³⁺ nanoparticles (see Fig. S1†) were prepared using a modified two-step thermolysis process, which occurs *via* decomposition of lanthanide oleates.³³ Initially, the β -NaYF₄: Yb³⁺,Er³⁺ core nanoparticles were synthesized, and then they were used as the seed crystals for depositing the β -NaYF₄:Yb³⁺, Nd³⁺ shell on top of them. As we have shown previously, shell thickness may be controlled by varying the reaction time for any amount of lanthanide precursors.³⁴

In general, there are two types of temperature-dependent mechanisms which can be used for temperature sensing based on luminescent nanoparticles: (i) thermalization of energy levels ruled by Boltzmann (B) distribution and (ii) phonon assisted energy transfer ruled by the Miyakava–Dexter (MD) model.³⁵ In the former process, the luminescence intensity ratio (LIR) of the thermally populated–depopulated states versus the population of the metastable level is considered. In the latter case, the temperature-dependent energy transfer probability between the donor (D) and acceptor (A) is quantified by means of the luminescence intensity ratio between the emission bands of D and A or by means of the luminescence lifetimes of the

donor. As a significant advancement of the current work as compared to state-of-the-art, both B and MD phenomena have been employed simultaneously, though they worked independently within a single core-shell nanoparticle.

Upon 808 nm irradiation of YbEr@YbNd nanoparticles, the electrons are optically excited from the ground state of Nd³⁺ (⁴I_{9/2}) ions up to its excited state (⁴F_{5/2}), which is followed by fast non-radiative population of the metastable state (⁴F_{3/2}). Then, different radiative and non-radiative processes can take place (Fig. 1) in sequence, starting from (a) Nd³⁺ emission and in parallel, (b) the energy transfer between Nd³⁺ and Yb³⁺, (c) energy migration through the Yb³⁺ network, followed by (d) energy transfer up-conversion between Yb³⁺ and Er³⁺ and finally (e) by green Er³⁺ emission. In the case of neodymium, the most intense emission bands, which are localized at ~1060 nm and ~880 nm, correspond to the ⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{11/2} and ⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{9/2} transitions, respectively. Owing to efficient Nd³⁺ → Yb³⁺ ET, ytterbium ions emit in the NIR ²F_{5/2} → ²F_{7/2} at 980 nm. The Nd³⁺ → Yb³⁺ energy transfer efficiency is ruled by the Miyakava–Dexter model,³⁵ and we have recently reported that the luminescence intensity ratio defined as the ratio between the respective emission bands (LIR₁(T) = I(1060)/I(980)) can be applied (Fig. 2b) as a temperature sensor.²²

Fig. 1 Idea of broadening the sensitivity range of the ratiometric optical nano-thermometer. Upon irradiation of YbEr@YbNd nanoparticles (A) at 808 nm, a series of energy transfers occur (A, B), starting from the energy transfer (ET) through photo-excited Nd³⁺ and Yb³⁺, followed first by energy migration (EM) through the Yb³⁺ network, and next by efficient Yb³⁺ to Er³⁺ energy transfer upconversion (ETU). The ratio between the emission intensities at 1060 nm (Nd³⁺) and 980 nm (Yb³⁺) – LIR₁, as well as the ratio between the emission intensities at 520 and 540 nm (Er³⁺) – LIR₂ are temperature dependent.

As soon as Yb³⁺ is populated, energy migration occurs and a significant amount of energy is pumped into the core of the NPs, where Yb³⁺ can interact with the Er³⁺ ions. Efficient ETU between Yb³⁺ secondary sensitizers and Er³⁺ activators leads to the ⁴F_{7/2} state population, which is followed by the step-wise population of ²H_{11/2} and ⁴S_{3/2}. The higher ²H_{11/2} energy level is thermally populated from ⁴S_{3/2}, hence, the increase of its emission intensity is proportional to the temperature rise (Fig. 2a). Both levels are capable of emitting photons, and the

temperature dependent luminescence intensity ratio between 520 and 540 nm emission ($LIR_2(T) = I(520 \text{ nm})/I(540 \text{ nm})$), which correspond to the ${}^2H_{11/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ and ${}^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transitions, is proportional to temperature, as described by Boltzmann's law.^{10,15,16,36}

The presented nano-thermometer exhibited efficient NIR-to-Vis and NIR-to-NIR emission from the YbEr or NdYb components, respectively, under a single 808 nm excitation line (the setup is presented in Fig. S2†). The temperature variations of both ${}^2H_{11/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ (Er^{3+}) to ${}^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ (Er^{3+}) emission bands as well as ${}^4F_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{11/2}$ (Nd^{3+}) to ${}^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^2F_{7/2}$ (Yb^{3+}) emission bands for YbEr@YbNd nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 2a and b, respectively. They have been studied in the 103 to 443 K temperature range indicating the possibility of broadening the temperature sensitivity range. To study the impact of the temperature on LIR_1 and LIR_2 figure of merits, their normalized values were compared (Fig. 2c). The LIR_1 and LIR_2 display opposite and complementary behavior.

Fig. 2 Spectral properties of the double range nano-thermometer (3% Nd^{3+}). (a) Green anti-Stokes and (b) NIR Stokes emission spectra, as well as (c) LIR and (d) sensitivity for the Vis and NIR spectral range versus external temperature.

The LIR_1 demonstrates flat performance ($\Delta LIR_1 \sim 55\%$) in the 150–325 °C range where LIR_2 changes significantly ($\Delta LIR_2 \sim 97\%$) and, oppositely, the LIR_1 becomes responsive and sensitive ($\Delta LIR_1 \sim 98\%$) in the 325–450 °C range where LIR_2 becomes gradually saturated ($\Delta LIR_2 \sim 57\%$). The presented changes indicate that the sensitivity of the temperature determination using these two luminescent thermometers differ at different temperatures. The impact of the LIR_1 and LIR_2

luminescent thermometers' sensitivity was determined according to the simple formula $S_P(T) = [\text{LIR}_P(T)]^{-1} [\Delta\text{LIR}_P(T)/\Delta T]$ ($P = \text{process 1 or 2}$) (Fig. 2d).

The sensitivity of the LIR_2 thermometer decreases slowly and proportionally to the rising temperature from 0.02 K^{-1} at 200 K to 0.01 K^{-1} above 350 °C. Simultaneously, LIR_1 sensitivity increases from almost 0 K^{-1} at 200 K to over 0.021 K^{-1} at 370 K. Both figures of merit, *i.e.* the LIR absolute values and sensitivities of both the thermometer components indicate clearly the possibility of broadening the temperature sensing range. Moreover, using a double luminescent thermometer working in two different spectral ranges allows for self-referenced temperature determination, for which, every single readout from one part of the sensor can be compared with the respective measurements using the second temperature sensor. Many studies concerning up-converting NPs confirmed how strongly up-conversion emission properties depend on both the sensitizer and activator ion concentrations.^{17,37–40} As was recently showed by us, the Yb^{3+} concentration has an important influence on both the operating temperature range as well as on the sensitivity of Nd^{3+} , Yb^{3+} co-doped luminescent thermometers.²² In the case of YbEr@YbNd nanoparticles the concentration of Nd^{3+} ions, which plays the role of primary absorber (sensitizer), will also affect the temperature sensitivity. To determine the influence of sensitizer content (x) on the spectroscopic and thermometric properties of YbEr@YbNd_x nanoparticles, the above described studies of $\text{LIR}(T)$ and $S(T)$ have been performed for a series of samples, with $x = 1\%$, 3% , 10% and 15% of Nd^{3+} with respect to Y^{3+} ions (Fig. S3†). As expected, the Nd^{3+} concentration did not affect the value of visible LIR_2 , however, a strong change in LIR_1 with the Nd^{3+} amount was observed, which most probably is due to the concentration-dependent Nd^{3+} emission intensity (Fig. S3†). The increase of the Nd^{3+} concentration enhances the $\text{Nd}^{3+}\text{--Nd}^{3+}$ energy transfers *via* parasitic cross relaxation (${}^4\text{F}_{3/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{9/2}$) \rightarrow (${}^4\text{I}_{15/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$) (CR) which dims Nd^{3+} emission intensity and increases that of LIR_2 . It is interesting to note that the sensitivity $S(T)$ of temperature sensing for both NIR and Vis thermometers (LIR_1 and LIR_2 , respectively), increases almost linearly with Nd^{3+} concentration.

The highest sensitivity of the YbEr@YbNd luminescent thermometer was found for the highest amount ($15\% \text{ Nd}^{3+}$) and reached 0.019 and 0.015 for the LIR_2 and LIR_1 thermometers, respectively (Fig. 3). This effect results from the shortening of the average $\text{Nd}^{3+}\text{--Yb}^{3+}$ distance and thus facilitated Nd^{3+} to Yb^{3+} energy transfer. Further enhancement of the NIR thermometer sensitivity for even higher Nd^{3+} doping is expected, as well as enhanced absorption cross section and possibly, light induced

heating.¹⁸ As has been recently demonstrated, the sensitivity can also be boosted by an appropriate selection of detectors and detection ranges, in order to enhance the relative changes of spectral features in response to the temperature.⁴ Such combined, single particle theranostic tools, namely optically based nano-heaters and enhanced optical ratiometric nano-thermometers, could be of great importance for hyperthermia treatments. However, further careful optimization is necessary to balance the CR quenching, signal to noise ratio, and sensitivity issues.

Fig. 3 The sensitivity of NIR and Vis luminescent thermometers as a function of Nd³⁺ concentration.

It is important to underline that the two luminescent thermometers are spatially displaced into core and shell, thus providing freedom, flexibility and predictability, in contrast to homogeneously mixed ingredients. Whereas for low 2% Nd³⁺ concentration the Yb–Er upconversion is not affected in the spectral domain, the overall upconversion efficiency is typically 10 times lower under ~808 nm excitation as compared to 980 nm excitation at the same excitation power.⁴¹ To overcome this drawback, higher Nd³⁺ doping is required, which unavoidably shall initiate a whole gamut of further issues in the homogeneously co-doped Nd–Yb–Er temperature sensitive system, such as significant back Er³⁺ → Nd³⁺ energy transfer and quenching, which would further on hinder the adoption of such systems in practical use.

Another issue with lanthanide-doped (nano)thermometers (LNT) is linked to their temperature sensitivity range. Although numerous LNT have been shown to cover the $\Delta T = 100$ to 1000 K range, one compound is typically capable of covering the $\Delta T = 40$ to $\Delta T = 150$ K temperature range at once, because of the highly individual sensitivity of a given electronic transition to temperature. The latter owes to the susceptibility of these transitions and luminescence to numerous temperature sensitive processes, such as multi-phonon decay, energy transfer between rare

earth ions or quenching centers, population re-distribution due to Boltzmann statistics and phonon assisted processes (e.g. RE^{3+} – RE^{3+} , RE^{3+} –host, and RE^{3+} –CT) states.^{42,43} While the impact of these processes is difficult to envisage in homogeneously mixed hosts, designing active-core–active-shell NPs may help to intentionally design luminescent probes that exhibit predictable behavior. Such an approach will expand the functionality of single nanoparticles, through the “LEGO” like arrangement of known combinations of hosts and dopants.

Conclusions

In summary, we propose a novel design of an all-optical nano-thermometer, which combines the advantages offered by the active-core–active-shell approach, *i.e.* the capability of intentionally designing the chemical architecture of lanthanide-doped colloidal luminescent nanoparticles. The original purpose for designing Nd^{3+} co-doped up-converting ACAS nanoparticles was to circumvent the overheating of biological samples by shifting the excitation wavelengths from 980 to 808 nm to avoid absorption by water molecules. Other possibilities have been discovered in such ACAS NPs by achieving UV/blue up-conversion and thus Eu^{3+} or Tb^{3+} anti-Stokes emission^{7,44} which otherwise are difficult to obtain in conventional up-conversion schemes.^{45,46} Our current work paves the way to further expand the extraordinary properties of such ACAS nanoparticles, by a wise combination of the inherent features of known luminescent materials. More specifically, this is the first demonstration of deliberately designed luminescent nanoparticles, which enhance the temperature responsivity of colloidal nano-thermometers. Either their core or shell exhibited temperature sensitive luminescence in different spectral ranges and in different temperature ranges. The green Er^{3+} emission based thermometer (core) exhibited better performance at lower temperatures, while the Nd – Yb NIR thermometer (shell) was suited for a higher temperature range. As the outcome, the $YbEr@YbNd$ NPs broadened the temperature range for which highly sensitive temperature determination is possible. These advancements expand the range of nano-thermometry applications. In particular, after suitable bio-functionalization, such ACAS NPs may become theranostic tools for combined thermographic imaging and hyperthermia treatments of solid tissues, functional luminescent labeling, thermographic imaging of PCR microfluidic devices or fundamental thermometry studies *e.g.* apoptosis at cellular or sub-cellular resolution. The improved nano-thermometers may also find numerous other applications in industry, where increased precision (*e.g.* owing to no-cross talk double measurement), broad

temperature variability, environmental conditions (e.g. significant light absorption or scattering) place stringent conditions for remote temperature readout.

Experimental

Materials

Yttrium oxide (99.99%), ytterbium oxide (99.99%), erbium oxide (99.99%) and neodymium oxide (99.99%), acetic acid (99%), pure oleic acid and 1-octadecene (90%) were purchased from ALDRICH Chemistry. Ethanol (96% pure p.a.), *n*-hexane (95%) and acetone (pure p.a.) and chloroform were purchased from POCH S.A. (Poland). All the chemical reagents were used as received without future purification.

Preparation of lanthanide acetate

Stoichiometric amounts of the respective Y_2O_3 , Er_2O_3 , Yb_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3 lanthanide oxides were mixed with 50% aqueous acetic acid. The mixture was stirred and heated up to obtain a clear and transparent solution. The final precursor was obtained by evaporation of the solvents at pre-vacuum and further drying at 130 °C for 12 h.

Preparation of precursor for the nanoparticle synthesis

The lanthanide acetate – $(CH_3COO)_3Y$, $(CH_3COO)_3Yb$ and $(CH_3COO)_3Er$ or $(CH_3COO)_3Y$, $(CH_3COO)_3Yb$ and $(CH_3COO)_3Nd$ – 2.5 mmol were added to the flask with 15 ml oleic acid and 38 ml octadecene. The solution was stirred and heated up to 140 °C under vacuum for 30 min to form the $Ln(oleate)_3$ complex and to remove total oxygen and the remaining water. Next the temperature was lowered to 50 °C and 10 mmol ammonium fluoride (NH_4F) and 6.25 mmol sodium hydroxide ($NaOH$) dissolved in 20 ml of methanol were added to the reaction flask. The resulting cloudy mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at 70 °C. Next, the reaction temperature was increased and the methanol was evaporated.

Preparation of core and core–shell nanoparticles

After removing methanol, the solution was heated up to 300 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere and kept under such conditions for 1 hour. After the core nanoparticle formation, part of the solution was taken as the reference. Next, the nanoparticles were precipitated using acetone and *n*-hexane, centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for 10 min and washed with ethanol. Finally, the prepared reference core NPs were dispersed in chloroform.

After the core NP formation, the temperature of the solution was lowered to 250 °C and then the shell precursor was added drop-wise to the flask containing the core

NPs. Having admixed a constant amount of the shell's precursor, the temperature was again increased up to 300 °C and the reaction was continued for another one hour. After the synthesis, the temperature of the solution was lowered to room temperature. Finally, the nanoparticles were washed and precipitated according to the protocols described previously.

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